

ANALYSIS OF THE OPERATION OF BIG DATA TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. This article provides an analysis of the operation of big data technologies. The main characteristics of Big Data, many microservices, types of machine learning and neural networks are presented. The importance of Data mining analysis and its application in various fields are considered.

Keywords: *big data for business, big data parameters, crowdsourcing, simplest neural network, industrial Internet of Things platforms, simulation modeling.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Big data is not enough to just collect - it needs to be used somehow, for example, to make business development forecasts or test marketing hypotheses. And to use it, the data needs to be structured and analyzed. We will tell you what big data methods and technologies exist and how they help process big data.

Big Data, or big data for business, is like a coded message: if you decipher it, you will get precise coordinates to plot a course. Let's figure out how it works.

Big Data are arrays of information that help make informed decisions, they are also called data-driven, that is, based on data. They allow you to build highly accurate predictive models. Such models are used, for example, in NASA to reproduce all the details of a future mission. Special tools and equipment are required to collect, store and analyze big data. For example, instead of one PC or server for storing Big Data, many servers or data centers around the world are used [1,2].

II. METHODS

Big Data Parameters. The main characteristics of Big Data are defined as six "V's": Volume - from 150 GB per day. Velocity - speed. The volume and content of Big Data change every second, so it needs to be collected and processed using large computing capacities. For example, the FlightRadar24 service, which displays all aircraft routes online. Variety - diversity. An array of big data can include photos, videos and texts, files of different sizes and formats, data from many different sources. Regular data is usually homogeneous, for example, an Excel table with the full name of each employee. Veracity - reliability. Big data is collected only from sources that can be trusted, and accurate and objective methods are used for analysis. Therefore, corporations and international organizations make strategic decisions based on this data. Variability - variability. Big data is updated online, so its flow is unstable. It is affected by the speed of transmission, changing sources, user actions and even changing seasons. When analyzing data, all these factors must be taken into account and predicted. For example, flight data should be used with adjustments for flight delays and weather conditions that change routes. Value. The data itself means nothing, but based on it, you can draw deep conclusions and make informed decisions. For example, analyze traffic on the roads during the year and understand how best to build routes for public transport.

Big Data can also be: Structured - that is, already marked up according to certain parameters. Let's say, data on key medical indicators of patients: temperature, pressure, blood tests and ECG. Partially structured, for example, files of different formats with records of natural disasters in the region over the past five years. Unstructured, for example, photos, music and messages of all VK users.

Another important difference between big data and regular data is the distributed structure. This means that they can be managed and analyzed using many microservices.

Crowdsourcing. Usually, Big Data analysis is done by computers, but sometimes it is entrusted to people. Crowdsourcing exists for these purposes - involving a large group of people in solving a problem.

How it works. Let's say you have a large amount of raw data. For example, records of store sales, where products are often recorded with errors and abbreviations. For example, a Dexter drill with a 10 mAh battery is recorded as "Drill Dexter 10 mAh", "Drill Dexter 10", "Drill Dexter acc 10" and a dozen other ways. You find a group of people who are willing to pay to manually look through tables and bring such names to a single form [3,4].

Why and where it is used. Crowdsourcing is good if the task is one-time and there is no point in developing a complex artificial intelligence system to solve it. If

you need to analyze big data regularly, a system based on Data Mining or machine learning will most likely be cheaper than crowdsourcing. Machines are also better at complex analysis based on mathematical methods, such as statistics or simulation modeling.

Data Blending and Integration. What is it. Working with big data often involves collecting disparate data from different sources. To work with this data, you need to bring it together. You can't just upload it to one database - different sources may provide data in different formats and with different parameters. This is where data blending and integration comes in the process of bringing disparate information to a single form.

How does it work? To use data from different sources, the following methods are used: bring the data to a single format: recognize text from photographs, convert documents, translate text into numbers. Supplement the data. If there are two sources of data about one object, the information from the first source is supplemented with data from the second to get a more complete picture. Filter out redundant data: if a source collects unnecessary information that is not available for analysis, it is deleted [5,6].

Fig.1. Big data and other technologies

Why and where it is used. Data mixing and integration are needed if there are several different data sources, and you need to analyze this data in a complex.

For example, your store sells offline, through marketplaces and simply via the Internet. To get complete information about sales and demand, you need to collect a lot of data: cash receipts, inventory balances in the warehouse, online orders, orders through the marketplace, and so on. All this data comes from different places and usually has a different format. To work with them, they need to be brought to a single form.

Traditional data integration methods are mainly based on the ETL process - extraction, transformation and loading. Data is obtained from sources, cleaned and loaded into storage. Specialized tools of the big data ecosystem from Hadoop to NoSQL databases also have their own approach to extracting, transforming and loading data. After integration, big data is subject to further manipulation: analysis and so on.

Fig.2. How Big Data technologies work

The process goes like this: data is extracted, cleaned and processed, placed into a corporate data warehouse, and then taken out for analysis [7,8].

III. RESULTS

Machine learning and neural networks. Conventional computers are good at counting, but they are bad at some tasks that are easy for humans. For example, let's remember the example above: it is difficult for a machine to understand that "Drill Dexter 10 mAh", "Drill Dexter 10", "Drill Dexter acc 10" are the same device.

In order for a machine to be able to think like a human, it is necessary to build a structure similar to the human brain in it. Neural networks are such structures. They consist of many artificial neurons that form connections during training and can then analyze information.

Neural networks operate according to a single algorithm - they receive data at the input, "run" it through a network of their neurons and produce a result at the output, for example, assign the input data to a certain group.

In order for a neural network to work, it must first be trained - this process is called machine learning. Let's take an example. Let's imagine that you need to teach

a neural network to distinguish between men and women from a photo. To do this, you will need: Build a neural network - program artificial neurons to perceive input data and create connections. Give the neural network a cleaned sample - a database of faces clearly marked as female or male. This way, the neural network will understand what criteria to use to distinguish faces, that is, it will learn to do this. Test the neural network - give it a new cleaned sample, but do not tell it which faces are male and which are female. This will help you understand how often the neural network makes mistakes, and whether this level of errors is acceptable for you. After training and testing, you can use the neural network to process big data [9].

Fig.3. The diagram of the simplest neural network

This is what the simplest neural network looks like: information is fed to the input layer, processed internally, and the result is output through the output layer.

Why and where they are used. Neural networks are usually used when it is necessary to sort data, classify it and make decisions based on the input information. Neural networks are usually used for tasks that a person can handle: recognizing a face, sorting photos, identifying a fraudulent banking transaction based on a number of features. In such tasks, a neural network replaces dozens of people and allows you to make decisions faster.

VK Cloud (former MCS) has a service for developing applications based on machine learning. With it, your developers can quickly create neural networks without supporting their own expensive infrastructure.

Predictive analytics and big data. Often, it is necessary not only to analyze and classify old data, but also to make forecasts about the future based on it. For example, based on sales for the past 10 years, to assume what they will be next year.

Predictive analytics big data helps with such forecasts. The word "predictive" is derived from the English "predict" - "to predict, to forecast", so such analytics are sometimes called predictive.

The task of predictive analytics is to identify several parameters that affect the data. For example, we want to understand whether a large client will continue to cooperate with the company.

To do this, we study the database of past clients and see which "parameters" of clients influenced their behavior. This could be the volume of purchases, the date of the last transaction, or even non-obvious factors like the duration of communication with managers. After that, using mathematical functions or neural networks, we build a model that can determine the probability of refusal for each client and warn about it in advance.

Why and where it is used. Predictive analytics is needed wherever it is necessary to make forecasts. Traders were among the first to use it to predict exchange rate fluctuations. Now such analytics are used in various areas to predict: sales and customer behavior in marketing; cargo delivery time in logistics; fraud in banking and insurance; company growth and financial indicators in any area.

Industrial Internet of Things platforms are being implemented at enterprises and factories: sensors collect arrays of data on the operation of equipment, and then analytics systems, including those based on machine learning, process them and predict breakdowns and maintenance schedules. Such IoT platforms can be deployed in the cloud: this reduces the costs of developing, managing and operating IoT services and solutions [10,11].

Simulation modeling. What is it. Sometimes a situation arises in which you need to see how some indicators will behave when others change. For example, how sales will change if you raise the price. It is inconvenient to conduct such experiments in the real world - it is expensive and can lead to serious losses. Therefore, in order not to experiment with a real business, you can build a simulation model. Let's imagine that we want to see how different factors affect store sales. To do this, we take the data: sales, prices, number of customers and everything else related to the store. Based on this data, we build a store model.

Then we make changes to it - we raise and lower prices, change the number of sellers, increase the flow of visitors. All these changes affect other indicators - we can choose the most successful innovations and implement them in a real store.

Simulation modeling is a bit like predictive analytics. Only we predict the future not based on real, but on hypothetical data.

A simulation model can be built without big data. But the more data, the more accurate the model, since it takes into account more factors.

Why and where it is used. Wherever you need to test some hypotheses, but testing them on a real business would be too expensive. For example, a large-scale change in prices for a long time can collapse a business, so before such a step it is better to test on a model.

It is important to remember that even a large-scale model often does not take into account all the factors. Therefore, modeling can give an incorrect result, the model must be transferred to reality taking into account all the risks [12].

IV. DISCUSSION

Statistical analysis. The essence of statistics is to collect data, calculate it according to certain criteria and get a specific result, usually in percentages.

One of the problems with statistics is unreliable results on small samples. For example, out of 20,000 people, 15,000 are dissatisfied with the service, but the company only surveyed 100 - and the sample included 80 loyal customers. It turns out that 80% of respondents are satisfied with the service, which does not coincide with reality.

Big data helps make statistics more reliable. The more information you collect, the more accurate the result. If instead of 100 customers you survey 10,000, the survey results can already be considered reliable [13,14].

Different methods are used to obtain accurate statistical results. Here are some of them: Simple calculation of percentages. Calculating average data values, sometimes distributed into groups. Correlation analysis, which helps to identify relationships and understand how changes in some data will affect others. A method of dynamic series that estimates the intensity and frequency of data changes over time.

Why and where it is used. Wherever data needs to be counted for analysis. Statistical analysis is often used as part of other technologies - for example, it is necessary for simulation modeling or predictive analytics.

Data mining. What is it. Big data is a large array of heterogeneous data. In order for them to be useful, some useful patterns need to be found in them: similarities, differences, common categories, and so on. The process of finding such patterns is called data mining - data mining, or deep data analysis.

We take big data and "extract" new useful data from it using various technologies: all kinds of classification, modeling and forecasting methods based on the use of decision trees, neural networks, genetic algorithms and other techniques. Statistical methods are often included in data mining methods.

Data mining solves several main problems: Classification - distribution of data into pre-known classes. Clustering - distribution of data into groups based on the

degree of similarity to each other. For example, creating different customer profiles based on their behavior in the store. Association - searching for repeating data patterns. For example, identical sets of products in customer receipts. Regression analysis - finding important factors that influence a given parameter. Deviation analysis - identifying atypical data that differs sharply from the usual. Why and where it is used. Wherever it is necessary to extract some trends and patterns from big data. The solution to most company data-related problems comes down to one or another data mining task or a combination of them. For example, risks can be assessed using regression analysis, customers can be segmented using clustering, demand can be predicted by identifying associations in data, and so on.

Fig.4. Data mining combines different methods and technologies for working with data

Visualization of analytical data. What is it. To make the results of analytics easier to evaluate and use, data visualization is used to work with big data. That is, they are presented in the form of graphs, diagrams, histograms, 3D models, maps and icons. Visualization is usually the final stage, a demonstration of the results of analysis carried out in other ways. For example, you built a simulation model and display the result of its work in the form of a graph that shows sales fluctuations depending on price changes. Or compared sales in different regions and visualized this data on a map, coloring the regions in different colors.

Usually, analysis tools can also visualize data, since it is difficult to display the results of work without visualization. There are many tools for data visualization, for example: Tableau, Qlik, Orange.

Why and where it is used. Everywhere where people need to work with data. For example, if you need to evaluate the results of processing or demonstrate them to a manager or executive.

Fig. 5. An example of visualizing customer behavior in a store in the form of a heat map

V. CONCLUSION

Technologies for big data analytics: Crowdsourcing - manual analysis by a large number of people. Data mixing and integration - bringing data from different sources to one form, clarifying and supplementing data. Machine learning and neural networks - creating programs that can analyze and make decisions, building logical connections. Predictive analytics - predicting the future based on collected data. Simulation modeling - building models based on big data that help conduct an experiment in computer reality, without affecting the real state of affairs. Statistical analysis - calculating data using formulas and identifying trends, similarities and patterns in them. Data Mining - a technology for extracting new significant information from a large volume of data. Visualization - presenting big data and the results of their analysis in the form of convenient graphs and diagrams that are understandable to humans.

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